

Metal Complexes of some Model Peptide Derivatives. Part-IX. Complexation Equilibria of Cobalt-, Nickel-, Copper- and Zinc(II) with Salicyloyl-glycylglycine

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Combined pH-metric and spectrophotometric study on the complexation equilibria of Co^{II} , Ni^{II} , Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} with the model peptide ligand, salicyloyl-glycylglycine, $(o)\text{HO}-\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{CONHCH}_2\text{CONHCH}_2\text{COOH}$ provided evidence of formation of only 1:1 metal:ligand complexes, $\text{M}(\text{H}_-, \text{L})^{2-}$, in which the metal ions are coordinated by the two deprotonated amide nitrogen atoms along with phenolic and carboxylic oxygen atoms of the ligand. Proton-ligand and metal-ligand constants were determined in 50% (v/v) ethanol-water medium at a fixed ionic strength ($I=0.2 \text{ M NaNO}_3$) at $30 \pm 0.1^\circ$. The complexation equilibria were worked out and correlated with the mode of bonding of the ligand.

METAL-ligand equilibria with amino acids and small peptides provided models for metal-protein interactions in the enzymes¹. We have described the modes of bonding of the amide moiety with Cu^{II} ion and the influence thereto of an adjacent $\text{C}=\text{C}$ moiety in an earlier paper². In this paper we present the results of our equilibrium study on the complex formation of the model peptide ligand salicyloyl-glycylglycine, $(o)\text{HO}-\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{CONHCH}_2\text{CONHCH}_2\text{COOH}$ (hereafter, SGG or LH_2) with Co^{II} , Ni^{II} , Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} . The purpose of the present equilibrium study is to work out the mode of bonding of two adjacent amide moieties to metal ions when a carboxylic and a phenolic moieties are present at suitable positions to provide coordination.

Experimental

The ligand SGG was prepared by condensing acetylsalicyloylchloride with glycylglycine in the presence of aqueous NaOH (pH 9–10), followed by acidification with ice-cold dilute HCl in a ice-water bath (5°). The precipitated acetylsalicyloyl-glycylglycine was hydrolysed by digestion with dilute 1N HCl on a steam-bath for 1 h to yield salicyloyl-glycylglycine, which crystallised on cooling the reaction mixture to room temperature. The product was recrystallised from hot water and air-dried, m.p. 236° (Found: eqv. wt. 252.02; C, 52.31; H, 4.70; N, 11.08. $\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_{12}\text{O}_5\text{N}_2$ calcd. for: eqv. wt. 252.00; C, 52.38; H, 4.76; N, 11.11%); ν_{max} (KBr) 3220 (OH), 3000 (NH), 1700 (COOH), 1650 (amide I), 1535 (amide II), and 1290 cm^{-1} (amide III); λ_{max} (EtOH) 300, 240 and 212 nm (log ϵ 3.63, 4.76 and 4.95 respectively). All the other reagent (AnalaR) solutions were prepared in purified ethanol and double-distilled CO_2 -free water. Standard solutions of

metal ions and carbonate-free NaOH solution were prepared as described in literature^{4,5}.

Procedure for the pH-metric study was the same as described earlier^{2,6}. The following solutions each of initial volume 25 ml in 50% (v/v) ethanol-water medium were prepared for the pH-metric study: (i) 0.01 M HNO_3 , (ii) 0.01 M $\text{HNO}_3 + 0.01 \text{ M SGG}$, (iii) 0.01 M $\text{HNO}_3 + 0.001 - 0.002 \text{ M metal nitrate}$, (iv) 0.01 M $\text{HNO}_3 + 0.01 \text{ M SGG} + 0.001 - 0.002 \text{ M metal nitrate}$.

Ionic strength of the solutions were fixed at $I=0.2 \text{ M}$ by adding requisite amounts of NaNO_3 . The solutions were placed in a thermostat to attain the desired temperature ($30 \pm 0.1^\circ$). All the solutions were titrated with 0.125 M NaOH, prepared in the same solvent medium and having the desired ionic strength and temperature. Each titration was performed thrice. pH, volume data as were the averages of three titrations were used for the calculation of equilibrium constants.

Equilibrium constants were calculated by running the programme scogs⁷ on a PC XT computer system. Preliminary values of some of the constants supplied to the computer as input data were calculated by analysing the pH-titration curves (Fig. 1) according to the procedure of Irving and Rossotti⁸. Ionisation constant of water in the mixed solvent media as given by Wooley, Horkot and Hepler⁹ and ionic activity coefficient of hydrogen ion as given by Harned and Owen¹⁰ were used. Analytical hydrogen ion concentrations, $[\text{H}]$, were calculated from the pH meter readings following the usual procedures^{11,12}. The results are summarised in Table 1.

$M(OH)^+$, $M(OH)_2$ etc. could arise according to

$$K_M^H = ([H][M(OH)^+]) / [M] \quad (3)$$

$$K_M^{2H} = ([H]^2[M(OH)_2]) / [M] \quad (4)$$

The constants K_M^H and K_M^{2H} were evaluated by computing the pH-titration data of the solutions (iii) containing the free metal ions in the absence of the ligand (LH_2). Titrations were discontinued at the appearance of turbidity, obviously due to $M(OH)_2$.

Spectrophotometric study of the M^{2+} -SGG mixtures ($M=Cu^{II}$ and Ni^{II}) at pH 9.50 by mole-ratio method¹³ indicated the formation of only 1:1 metal:ligand complexes in these systems. The formation of 1:1 metal:ligand complex out of M^{2+} and LH^- ligand species with release of $3H^+$ per M^{2+} could take place only according to the following complexation equilibria:

$$K_{M+LH}^{3H} = ([H]^3[M(H_{-2}L)^{2-}]) / ([LH^-][M]) \quad (5)$$

where, the ligand, $(H_{-2}L)^{4-}$ ion in the complexes represents the fully deprotonated ligand species, $(o)O^-C_3H_4CON^-CH_2CON^-CH_2COO^-$, derived from the L^{2-} ion after substitution of the two amide protons by M^{2+} ions.

For calculation of the formation constants K_{M+LH}^{3H} using the SCOGS programme⁷ the following species, viz. LH^- , L^{2-} , M^{2+} , $M(OH)^+$, $M(OH)_2$ and $M(H_{-2}L)^{2-}$ were considered to exist in the complexation equilibria. The refined values of K_{COOH}^H , K_{OH}^H , K_M^H , K_M^{2H} and estimated values of K_{M+LH}^{3H} were supplied to the computer as the input data. The computer gave the values of the constants K_{M+LH}^{3H} and also the concentration distributions of the complex species (Figs. 2-5) at different pH values as the output.

Fig. 2. Species distribution curves of Co^{II} -SGG system: (1) LH_2 , (2) LH^- , (3) L^{2-} , F_M , Co^{II} , (4) $Co(OH)^+$, (5) $Co(OH)_2$ and (6) $Co(H_{-2}L)^{2-}$.

Fig. 3. Species distribution curves of Ni^{II} -SGG system: (1) LH_2 , (2) LH^- , (3) L^{2-} , F_M , Ni^{II} , (4) $Ni(OH)^+$, (5) $Ni(OH)_2$ and (6) $Ni(H_{-2}L)^{2-}$.

Fig. 4. Species distribution curves of Cu^{II} -SGG system: (1) LH_2 , (2) LH^- , (3) L^{2-} , F_M , Cu^{II} , (4) $Cu(OH)^+$, (5) $Cu(OH)_2$ and (6) $Cu(H_{-2}L)^{2-}$.

Fig. 5. Species distribution curves of Zn^{II} -SGG system: (1) LH_2 , (2) LH^- , (3) L^{2-} , F_M , Zn^{II} , (4) $Zn(OH)^+$, (5) $Zn(OH)_2$ and (6) $Zn(H_{-2}L)^{2-}$.

Concentration of $\text{Cu}(\text{H}_{-2}\text{L})^{2-}$ ion was about 98% around pH 7.0–7.5, while the corresponding complexes with Co^{II} , Ni^{II} and Zn^{II} reached their maximum concentration ($\approx 95\%$) around pH 8–9. The hydroxo complexes $\text{M}(\text{OH})^+$ and $\text{M}(\text{OH})_2$ occurred with the Co^{II} , Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} -SGG systems, but these could not be identified with the Zn^{II} -SGG system. However, the concentration of these hydroxo complexes particularly the electroneutral $\text{M}(\text{OH})_2$ complexes were too low (Figs. 2–5) to exceed their solubility products. In fact no turbidity could be observed in any of these metal-ligand mixtures.

Release of three protons per metal (eqn. 5) could be explained on the basis of metal-promoted deprotonation of the two amide moieties along with the phenolic OH group of the ligand, LH^- ion. Therefore, the metal ions in the $\text{M}(\text{H}_{-2}\text{L})^{2-}$ complexes are coordinated by the two deprotonated amide nitrogen atoms and the phenolic oxygen atom of the ligand, $\text{H}_{-2}\text{L}^{4-}$ ion. Such mode of coordination also possibly brought the carboxylate moiety of the ligand at a position suitable for chelation (1).

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$\text{M}(\text{H}_{-2}\text{L})$, $\text{M}=\text{Co}, \text{Ni}, \text{Cu}$ and Zn

The red-violet colour of Cu^{II} -SGG mixture at $\text{pH} > 5.5$ was indicative of coordination of deprotonated amide nitrogen atoms to Cu^{II} ion in the complex. The observed λ_{max} (540 nm) was quite

close to those of square-planar Cu^{II} complexes having the Cu^{II} ion coordinated by two deprotonated amide nitrogen atoms in analogous complexes^{1,4}. The Cu^{II} -SGG complex was found to be 6–7 log units more stable than the corresponding complexes with Co^{II} , Ni^{II} and Zn^{II} with this ligand obviously due to the attainment of its favoured square-planar geometry^{1,6}.

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